

*Cross-sectoral planning decision-making
platform to foster climate action*

Summary results of Almería case study (CS5)

Policy Brief

September 2025

H2020-LC-GD-2020-2: LC-GD-9-2-2020. Developing end-user products and services for all stakeholders and citizens supporting climate adaptation and mitigation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037104.

Rethinking Almería province in a changing climate

Key findings

- Climate change is expected to exacerbate water pressures by raising temperatures and reducing rainfall, thereby pushing irrigation demand beyond sustainable limits.
- Prioritization of water-use efficiency by implementing policies is essential to achieve a 60% decrease in water demand in agricultural, domestic, and economic sectors.
- Increasing desalination capacity and the promoting the reuse of treated water will reduce pressures on aquifers.
- Implementation of medium-to-high values for policy intensities in those policies that directly affect the water supply (desalination and water reuse) and the water demand (efficiency) is necessary to avoid continuous aquifer overexploitation.
- Planning for energy-water trade-offs should be implemented by incorporating strategies for managing the rising energy demand linked to alternative water sourcing.
- Promotion of adaptive land-use changes will support the transition from rainfed to irrigated crops, and ensure the coupling of these changes with sustainable water management policies.

Keywords: Almería; land-use; LAMS; water security; groundwater; agriculture; energy; system dynamics; adaptation; mitigation; implementation of climate solutions

Executive Summary

The province of Almería is located in South-Eastern Spain. Almería is covered by dry land and hosts Europe's only desert. Even though it is the driest region in Spain, the region has a well-developed agricultural sector. Almería province has the highest concentration of greenhouses in the world, producing over 3.5 million tons of fruits and vegetables a year. Horticultural activities, even if very profitable, create particularly high water demand, while extensive groundwater use further stresses the fragile hydrological system.

This document presents the most relevant **land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS)** for the province of Almería, with a focus on water management as the central issue of assessment.

Source: <https://pixabay.com/>

In Almería, water security should be supported by an expansion of alternative water sources, contributing to the reduction of groundwater extraction. These alternative sources are key for long-term agricultural resilience, though their production requires careful management of energy demand. This policy brief targets regional policymakers, local authorities, farmer cooperatives, and renewable energy developers.

rethinkaction.eu

Background & Policy Context

Climate change is a risk multiplier that can exacerbate existing risks and crises through the interaction of climatic and non-climatic drivers. This includes land use change, which plays a crucial role in achieving the ambitious targets for climate resilience and neutrality in the European Union (EU) by 2050, as outlined in the framework of the EU Green Deal strategy ([Chiriaco et al., 2025¹](#)). In this context, the RethinkAction (H2020) project co-develops land-use-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS) with stakeholders across six EU case studies to reduce land-use-based emissions from various land-use types, supporting the objectives of the EU Green Deal.

¹ Chiriaco, M.V. et al. (2025). A catalogue of land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions to tackle climate change. *Sci Data* 12, 166 [[doi](#)].

High-resolution land use map of the **Almería province**. Source: RethinkAction project.

Almería's semi-arid climate makes the province highly vulnerable to severe water scarcity, a challenge amplified by its reliance on agriculture, which depends on irrigation to sustain crop production.

Shrubland is the most prominent land use, but irrigated land (including greenhouses) and rainfed land are also relevant in coastal and interior areas of the province respectively. Land use patterns also highlight the importance of agriculture, as crops occupy a large share of the case study.

Air temperature for scenario SSP5-8.5 and period 2041-2070. Source: RethinkAction Platform.

Climate & Geographic Focus for LAMS

A severe worsening of extreme events linked to temperature, precipitation, and wind is observed in Shared Socio-Economic Pathways SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5. These future scenarios predict that the rise in temperatures, increase in evapotranspiration, and the decline in precipitation will further reduce water availability in aquifers, rivers, and reservoirs, whereas demand from human consumption and agriculture will continue to grow. This combination risks deteriorating water quality and heightening competition for resources, particularly between the tourism and agriculture sectors.

Land-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS) were prioritized by stakeholders and are central to ensure that Almería province remains productive, climate-resilient, and ecologically sustainable.

Bridging Science and Society for Climate-Resilience Development

RethinkAction used state-of-the-art tools to connect climate scenarios with land-use decisions and policy options. The applied methodology combined climate modelling, land-use analysis, stakeholder engagement, and System Dynamics modelling to co-design actionable pathways. A participatory, multi-scale approach was applied, combining quantitative modelling with multiple stakeholder co-creation workshops across six case studies to evaluate different future alternatives.

Data collection, modelling, and policy analysis were carried out. A total of 5 basic *Essential Climate Variables* (Basic-ECVs) and 24 Derived-ECVs were downscaled to assess future exposures, followed by the identification of suitable LAMS based on both a literature review and multicriteria analysis, and their suitability at the local scale. In addition, crop yield anomalies were analysed in AquaCrop to assess the future crop yields and climate change conditions. Local stakeholders were involved in the evaluation of the potential risks across sectors through impact chains and the selection of potential packages of solutions, along with the main potential drivers and barriers of the region.

Local workshop three in Almería (January 2024).
Source: RethinkAction project.

For essential climate variables, Aquacrop, risk quantification, and local system dynamic modelling, the RethinkAction project used Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs) SSP1-2.6 (with lower emissions), SSP2-4.5 (with mid-range emissions) and SSP5-8.5 (highest emissions).

Translating Data into Action

The province will experience a notable shift in climate particularly in a long-term period. Mainly in SSP 5-8.5, the decreasing impact each month goes around -20% and -60% compared to the historical period, in a province where already the precipitation is little. Longer drought periods and more intense water scarcity will threaten water security even more. Concurrently, the frequency of extreme rainfall events is expected to grow raising the likelihood of flash floods.

The evapotranspiration is increasing in Almería, following a similar trend for both historical and future scenarios. This is due to the rising temperatures and more frequent heatwaves, which intensify water loss from soil and plants.

On the other hand, wind speed is slowly decreasing. In 2100 the mean wind speed would be slower than in 1985 by 0.2m/s.

Temperatures are expected to **increase up to +7°C by 2100 under SSP5-8.5**. The value of **temperature** is a **key indicator** that will have significant impact on the **future aridity** of the province, thereby directly affecting livelihoods and multiple vulnerable sectors.

Anomalies of the mean temperature for Almería comparing the period 2071-2100 with the historical (1985 - 2015) for SSP 1.2.6, 2.4.5 and 5.8.5. Source: RethinkAction project.

AquaCrop results show increases in barley, up to 25% for SSP2-4.5 (2041-2070). It is expected that maize productivity can remain for the most part constant. Tomato and watermelon crops were modelled considering greenhouse conditions. Their yields will increase by up to 30% and 56% respectively.

This information was fed into the simulation of the local system dynamics model, which can be used in the RethinkAction platform to test the policies and trade-offs. The results confirm that water management is the region’s most vulnerable sector. Overextraction of aquifers has reduced both the quantity (fig. below) and quality of water, creating severe challenges for key economic activities such as agriculture. Greenhouse farming, producing millions of tons of fruit and vegetables for EU markets, is especially dependent on irrigation which is a major cause of scarce water resources.

Considering the most relevant risks, stakeholders had chosen specific LAMS for water management and agriculture sectors. The LAMS displayed are “Water use efficiency: improve agriculture irrigation efficiency”, “Increased use of treated wastewater” and “Sustainable agriculture intensification”.

Stakeholder-Chosen LAMS

Water use efficiency:
improve agriculture irrigation

Increase use of
treated wastewater

Sustainable
agriculture

Conclusions

The local analysis of Almería province highlights its high vulnerability to climate change, driven by its territorial and climatic conditions. To address these challenges, the following policies are recommended: improving water use efficiency, expanding desalination and wastewater treatment, increasing irrigated cropland, and scaling up renewable energy deployment. These measures, developed through the local SD model and stakeholder feedback, could enhance resilience in key sectors such as water management and agriculture. They would foster sustainable agricultural growth while ensuring a more efficient use of scarce water resources. The key outcomes described are available in the Resources section of the [RethinkAction website](#) and in the [RethinkAction platform](#).

Impact chains were used to analyse these complex vulnerable conditions, considering all the factors involved. They are a tool that considers all the risk components and synthesizes the complex connections between them. They were quantified following ([Barilari et al., 2025](#)) and the results are available in the [RethinkAction platform](#).

Three **impact chains** were developed to define the risks in this case study: Risk of lower precipitation affecting farmers’ income (Agriculture); Risk of precipitation variability and heatwaves aggravating fresh water scarcity (Water management); Risk of reduced health of labour migrants in the horticulture sector (Society).

² Barilari, S. et al. (2025). Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment in the Province of Almeria (Spain) Under Different Climate Change Scenarios. *Climate*, 13(7), 141. [[doi](#)].

Universidad de Valladolid

Interested?
Visit the platform

www.rethinkaction.eu

Contact

Fundación CARTIF
E-Mail: rethinkaction@cartif.es
Phone: + 34 983 546 504
Fax: + 34 983 546 521

Parque Tecnológico de Boecillo, parcela 205
CP: 47151, Boecillo (Valladolid), Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037104.